

Synthesis of some biologically important pyrazoles and pyrazoline derivatives

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Abstract : 1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)ethanone (1) on treatment with 3-(benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (2) gave corresponding chalcones (3). These chalcones on treatment with DMSO/I₂ and hydrazine hydrate gave 2-heteroaryl chromones (4) and pyrazolines (6). The chromones (4) on treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave pyrazoles (5). Synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activities against *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923).

Keywords : Pyrazoline, synthesis, pyrazole, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Wide spread interest in the chemistry of benzofurans in a large number of natural products has attracted due to their biological activities and their potential applications as pharmacological agents. Several benzofuran ring systems bearing various substituents at the C-2 position are widely distributed in nature have antiviral, antioxidant and antifungal activities¹. Furthermore, most of the compounds prepared from 2-acetylbenzofurans have antimicrobial, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, fungicidal, weed-killing activity and used for treatment of cardiac arrhythmias²⁻⁹. On the other hand, compounds including pyrazole nucleus are known to possess analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiarrhythmic, muscle-relaxant, psychoanaleptic, anticonvulsant, hypotensive, monoamine oxidase inhibitor, antidiabetic and antibacterial activities¹⁰⁻¹⁷. Pyrazole derivative celebrex is a potential anti-inflammatory drug¹⁸.

Chromones having heterocyclic substituents at 2-position have been reported to possess antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal activities and also exhibit good phosphodiesterase inhibition activity¹⁹.

Pyrazolines are well known nitrogen containing five membered heterocyclic compounds. Several pyrazoline derivatives have been found to possess important biologi-

cal activities including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiviral and anti-HIV²⁰.

Keeping in view of biological activities associated with these heterocycles and in continuation of our work on chalcones²¹, chromones²², pyrazoles²³ and pyrazolines²⁴ here in we report synthesis of new heterocycles containing benzofuran nucleus.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation a series of novel 2-(3-benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-4*H*-chromen-4-ones (4) derivatives were synthesized by oxidative cyclization of (*E*) 3-(3-benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ones (3) in DMSO/I₂ and 2-(5-(3-(benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-3-yl)phenols (5) derivatives were synthesized by reaction of 2-(3-benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-4*H*-chromen-4-ones (4) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol and 2-(5-(3-benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-3-yl)phenols (6) derivatives were synthesized by reaction of (*E*) 3-(3-benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ones (3) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. The compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial activities against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida sp.*

The antibacterial screening suggests that the analogs with electron releasing substituents emerged as promising antibacterial agents.

3a : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3083 (-OH), 1637 (C=O), 1581 (C=C), 1493 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ) : 6.96–8.43 (14H, m, Ar-H), 7.07 (1H, d, HC=CH), 7.93 (1H,

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The completion of reactions was monitored by TLC. IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc on Jasco spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400 MHz instrument in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$, CDCl_3 and TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Varian GC-MS spectrometer.

(*E*) 3-(3-Benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ones (**3a-h**) :

Equimolar amount of compounds **1** (0.001 mol) and **2** (0.001 mol) were dissolved in 20 ml of alcohol in a round bottom flask. To this reaction mixture (40%) alc. KOH (10 ml) solution in water was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The contents were then poured into crushed ice and neutralized with HCl. The yellow solid thus obtained was filtered and crystallized from ethanol.

d, HC=CH), 8.39 (s, pyrazole), 12.93 (1H, s, -OH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 117.1, 118.2, 120.2, 123.4, 122.2, 127.1, 128.4, 129.4, 130.5, 132.4, 134, 135, 140.3, 191.2; Mass (m/z) : 407 (M+1).

2-(3-Benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-ones (**4a-h**) :

The compound **3** (0.001 mol) was dissolved in 15 ml DMSO. To this reaction mixture (0.001 mol) of I_2 was added. Contents were heated at 130–140 °C for 2 h and left overnight. Then the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice containing 3–4 g of sodium thiosulphate. The solid thus obtained was filtered and washed with cold water. The product obtained was crystallized from ethanol.

4c : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1636 (C=O), 1502 (C=N), 1300 (C-O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ) : 8.45 (1H, s, pyrazole), 6.75 (1H, s, chromone), 7.16–8.65 (13H, m, aromatic); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 23.2, 103.4,

110.1, 113.0, 118.8, 127.2, 128.3, 129.6, 130.2, 131.5, 132.4, 133.4, 135.4, 135.9, 192.2; Mass (*m/z*): 419 (M+1).

2-(5-(3-(Benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)phenols (5a-h) :

Compound 4a (0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.005 mol) was dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The contents were poured into crushed ice; the solid thus obtained was filtered and crystallized from ethanol.

5a : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3341 (-OH), 3047 (-N-H), 1502 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ) : 6.77-7.68 (15H, m, aromatic), 11.07 (1H, s, -OH), 8.11 (1H, s, pyrazole), 6.21 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 23.5, 24.5, 45.2, 49.1, 54.2, 119.1, 121.2, 129.8, 130.5, 135.1, 173.9; Mass *m/z* : 419 (M+1).

2-(5-(3-(Benzofuran-2-yl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)phenols (6a-h) :

Compound 3 (0.001 mol) was dissolved in 10 ml ethanol. To this reaction mixture 1 ml of hydrazine hydrate was added. Then reaction mixture was refluxed for 2-3 h. Then the contents were poured into crushed ice. The solid thus obtained was filtered and crystallized from ethanol.

6a : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3340 (-OH), 3047 (NH), 1502 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ) 11.07 (s, -OH), 8.11 (1H, s, pyrazole), 5.49 (1H, s, -NH), 3.22 (1H, m, pyrazoline), 3.74 (2H, m, pyrazoline), 6.77- 7.91 (15H, m, aromatic); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 25.7, 47.2, 49.8, 55.2, 116.7, 119.6, 126.8, 130.2, 132.1; Mass (*m/z*) : 421 (M+1).

Table 1. Characterization data of compounds 3, 4, 5 and 6(a-h)

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
3a	H	H	H	H	225	92
3b	H	CH ₃	Cl	H	199	80
3c	H	H	CH ₃	H	147	73
3d	Cl	H	Cl	H	278	74
3e	H	H	Cl	H	222	72
3f	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	192	76
3g	H	H	Br	H	164	74
3h	H	H	OCH ₃	H	161	70
4a	H	H	H	H	213	66
4b	H	CH ₃	Cl	H	211	65
4c	H	H	CH ₃	H	251	71
4d	Cl	H	Cl	H	155	67
4e	H	H	Cl	H	315	68

Table-1 (contd.)

4f	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	127	63
4g	H	H	Br	H	199	69
4h	H	H	OCH ₃	H	191	64
5a	H	H	H	H	218	82
5b	H	CH ₃	Cl	H	143	69
5c	H	H	CH ₃	H	267	71
5d	Cl	H	Cl	H	119	60
5e	H	H	Cl	H	> 300	70
5f	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	158	58
5g	H	H	Br	H	206	62
5h	H	H	OCH ₃	H	196	55
6a	H	H	H	H	221	72
6b	H	CH ₃	Cl	H	173	76
6c	H	H	CH ₃	H	172	75
6d	Cl	H	Cl	H	111	67
6e	H	H	Cl	H	225	89
6f	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	110	72
6g	H	H	Br	H	116	70
6h	H	H	OCH ₃	H	203	67

Antibacterial activity :

Compounds 3, 4, 5 and 6 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923) and *Candida sp.* using diffusion method and Muller-Hinton agar as culture medium. Compounds were found to be active, on comparing with control. Test solution was prepared by dissolving 1 mg (1000 μg) in 1 ml of DMSO and 0.1 ml (100 μg) of this solution was used for testing. The zone of inhibition was measured in mm. 4g was found to be active against Gram positive bacteria.

Table 2. Antibacterial activities of some representative compounds

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (ATCC 27853)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 25923)	<i>Candida sp.</i>
3a	-	-	-	-
3c	-	-	-	-
3d	-	-	-	-
3g	-	-	-	-
4a	-	-	-	-
4c	-	-	-	-
4d	-	-	-	-
4g	-	-	10 mm	-

Table-2 (contd.)

5a	-	-	-	-
5c	-	-	-	-
5d	-	-	-	-
5g	-	-	-	-
6a	-	-	-	-
6c	-	-	-	-
6d	-	-	-	-
6g	-	-	-	-
Gentamycin	23 mm	24 mm	23 mm	-
Cefixime	28 mm	-	15 mm	-
Ketoconazole	-	-	-	23 mm

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